

NetDRIVE Workshop

Durham University

September 24th to 26th, 2025

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Meeting page: <https://eng.ox.ac.uk/netdrive/events/>

Photo on front: [Durham City](#)

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3. Introduction

NetDRIVE held its annual Community Meeting in September 2025 with a focus on sustainable research computing for UKRI.

The meeting was held at Durham University's Ogden Centre for Fundamental Physics, hosted by the Institute for Computational Cosmology, and brought together people from many areas of UKRI funded research computing. The agenda included keynote presentations which stimulated discussion, and breakout sessions in which participants addressed specific challenges facing the community.

The meeting gave attendees a chance to meet the eight new champions for transformational change who joined the NetDRIVE project in September, with each champion given an opportunity to present their aims and ambitions for the project, and the community activities they are planning.

The meeting presented NetDRIVE's second call, a £1M funding call which includes £200K for early career researchers, as well as initiating working groups on Ethics and Sustainable Progress, Metrics and Reporting, Sustainability Clauses in Contracts and Conditionalities, and Short Format Online Training.

Participants were given a presentation on computing at Durham University and given a tour of one of the University's High-Performance Computing (HPC) facilities by Director of COSMA¹ HPC service Alastair Basden.

Plans for NetDRIVE's upcoming network meetings were shared with attendees, and NetDRIVE looks forward to hosting its next network meeting in Oxford in April 2026.

¹ COSMA (the COSmology MACHine) is the Distributed Research utilising Advanced Computing (DiRAC) Memory Intensive system and is located at Durham University (<https://www.durham.ac.uk/departments/academic/physics/cosma/>).

4. Working Groups

The initiation of four Working Groups (WGs) was discussed and agreed during the meeting. The scope of the WGs was clarified and people identified to take the process forward, including a phase of recruiting an appropriate range of members. In particular, aspects related to evaluation of the NetDRIVE project itself and its success in enhancing community sense of empowerment were taken out of the WG scope and placed back with the co-coordinators, as described in more detail below.

Working Groups will receive funds for meetings, including travel, accommodation, and reservation of meeting rooms from NetDRIVE. Costs in the range £10k to £15k are expected.

Each working group should aim to complete their work by September 2027, earlier if possible, and produce an Advice/Recommendations document which has been through community review. Additional supporting documents may be published. The procedure for advice and recommendations should be based around existing frameworks such as the Research Data Alliance and Health Data Research UK.

A WG on ethics and sustainable progress was proposed but the meeting recommended splitting the sustainable progress element, which relates to the continuity of the NetDRIVE community engagement activity. At the same time the scope of the Working Group on Metrics and Reporting was narrowed for focus on objective metrics of operational performance. The two elements taken out of these working groups will be picked up in the project reporting led by the co-ordinators, with the support of the integration lead (recruitment in progress). The transparency and community engagement element will be maintained by reviewing the reports in open meetings.

WG1: Short Format Training Material

This working group will create content for a short (10-20 minutes) video tutorial on sustainable research computing, using existing knowledge drawn from the community. The UKRI Environmental Sustainability team will work with contractors to convert the content into a video tutorial which will be freely available online.

WG2: Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses

Digital hardware purchased with UKRI funds should be provided with reliable information about the carbon footprint of manufacture and transport and carry appropriate certification of sustainability measures. In many cases the level of certification and quality of information provided will be limited by the lack of appropriate standards and mechanisms for independent certification. The working group will establish a pragmatic approach building on best practice and emerging standards.

WG3: Ethics (WGE)

WGE will develop an ethical framework for transformational change by reviewing existing frameworks for ethics and exploiting survey results to analyse the human impact of changes impacting on the DRI.

WG4: Metrics and Reporting (WGMAR)

WGMAR will develop a framework for monitoring and reporting on community progress towards net zero implementation, with a focus on measurable objective metrics. This will provide essential information on the practical success of actions introduced by NetDRIVE in terms of measurable or inferred impact on emissions.

Initial membership is listed in the table below.

Working Group Title	Initial Membership
WG1: Short Format Training Material	Andy Turner, Liz Ing-Simmons, Kirsty Pringle, Lorna Smith
WG2: Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses	Alex Owen, Lorna Smith, Michael Rudgyard, Tom Griffin, Alastair Basden,
WG3: Ethics (WGE)	Erinma Ochu
WG4: Metrics and Reporting (WGMAR)	Loïc Lannelongue, Michael Rudgyard, Emanuele Simili, Alex Owen, Kirsty Pringle, Jessica Huntley, Alistair Basden

Community Meetings

We are aiming for 3 multi-day community meetings in 2026. Venues and dates should be advertised 6 months in advance to allow potential delegates time to adjust schedules. The first of these will be in Oxford, we are looking for institutions to host the remaining two. The NetDRIVE project will pay reasonable costs, including room hire and staff time for the institution hosting the meetings.

Meetings should combine discussion of challenges specific to NetDRIVE with broader themes which impact on the NetDRIVE objectives.

Creating a New Reality: A Sustainable Digital Transformation

- 22nd and 23rd April, 2026; Oxford.
- Practical approaches to balancing residual greenhouse gas emissions based on Oxford offsetting principles will be explored; the shape of the decarbonised UK power market, exploring the potential roles of nuclear generation, enhanced storage and long-range distribution using hydrogen; the role of biofuels and biosphere carbon sequestration in a balanced carbon economy.

- Invited speakers will cover emerging nuclear and hydrogen technology which will enable net zero power supplies and the role of ratings agencies in establishing trust in carbon removal contracts.

Technology: Challenges and Opportunities

- Summer 2026
- Advances in digital technology will deliver huge benefits for the research community between now and 2040; facilities tracking the technology limits (~1000-fold in computational power per decade) are likely to see an increase in power demand of around 10-fold per decade. Tracking the technology limit will also require increasing the budget share of digital facilities.
- Do Universities need facilities which track the technology limits, or would it be enough to stay within existing power envelope and achieve around 100-fold increase in computational power per decade?

Cultural Change (including annual meeting)

- Autumn 2026
- How is digital technology transforming our research community and how can this transformation be harnessed to accelerate the transition to a fair and equitable society?

Appendix 1: Attendees

- Tariq A Majid
- Henry Addison
- Misael Alpizar Santana
- Veronica Araneta
- Alastair Basden
- Anjali Bhatt
- Christina Bremer
- Monika Byrne Svata
- Sarah Campbell
- Jeremy Cohen
- James Earl-Fraser
- Polly Eccleston
- Martin Farley
- Weronika Filingier
- Adrian Friday
- Luna Glucksberg
- Julio Cesar Gonzalez Saenz

- Marisa Goulden
- Tom Griffin
- Jessica Huntley
- Liz Ing-Simmons
- Pip Jackson
- Martin Jukes
- Gokmen Kilic
- Karen Lai
- Loic Lannelongue
- Lucy Li
- Chenguang Liu
- Cheng Marcello
- Joe Marsh Rossney
- Jacqueline Murphy
- Erinma Ochu
- Lisa Otty
- Alex Owen
- Kirsty Pringle
- Michael Rudgyard
- Emanuele Simili
- Lorna Smith
- Graeme Smith
- Sarah Sparrow
- Andrew Turner
- Sam Tygier

Appendix 2: Agenda

Wednesday

12:00 Welcome and coffee	
12:30-13:30: Lunch	
13:30 Session 1	
	Welcome and Introduction to Meeting [10 minutes]
	NetDRIVE and meeting objectives [30 minutes]
	Keynote 1: Alastair Basden: HPC at Durham [30 minutes] (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174359)
	Briefing for breakouts [20 minutes]
15:00	Coffee Break
15:15 Session 2	
	Breakout 1: Working Groups
16:30	Facility Tour (optional)

Thursday

09:00 Session 3	
	Welcome [10 minutes]
	Breakout 1 Feedback [Martin, 20 minutes]
	Keynote 2: Lisa Otty [30 minutes] (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174242)
	Green Skills Network+ & briefing [30 minutes] [Weronika Filinger]
10:30	Coffee Break
10:45	Session 4
	Green Skills Breakout [1 hour]
	Plenary discussion [30 minutes]
12:30	Lunch
13:45	Session 5
13:45	Keynote 3: Martin Farley: UKRI Environmental Sustainability (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174422)
14:15	Champions and Community Project short presentations
15:45	Afternoon Tea and Coffee
16:00	Session 6
	Working Groups: plenary discussion [30 minutes]
	Champions and PI panel discussion [30 minutes]
17:00	Day 2 Closes
19:00	Conference Dinner

Friday

09:00 Session 7	
	Welcome [10 minutes]
	Keynote 4: Adrian Friday [30 minutes] (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174483)
	Meetings for 2026 [50 minutes]
10:30	Coffee Break
10:45	Session 8
	Feedback and review of meeting objectives
	NetDRIVE forum and Network
	Tasks, Actions, Commitments
	Plenary Discussion
	Wrap-up
13:00	Lunch

Appendix 3: NetDRIVE AGM Breakout discussion summary

NetDRIVE Monitoring and Evaluation

A broad methodological process for monitoring and evaluation was discussed as follows:

- Establish an evaluation steering group
- Draft evaluation plan (based on template) considering:
 - Input, output, outcomes and impacts
 - Main users
 - Was there was a difference?
 - Monitoring and data requirements
- Agree evaluation plan with steering group
- Evaluate progress against plan

It was discussed that the existing Theory of Change (Leadership, Trust, Progress) should be used as a framework for the developed evaluation plan.

How community confidence could be measured was discussed with the following suggestions for inclusion in the evaluation plan:

- Attendance at meeting, the background of attendees
- Stories (ambassadors from the community) – evidencing individual action
- Representation from different research institutions – engaging key players?
- People talking on behalf of NetDRIVE
- Hours of training delivered
- Policy changes (UKRI, Universities)
- Numbers accessing best practice guides/training etc.
- Publications
- Community survey – can we meet NetZero objectives.
- People seeking NetDRIVE advice
- Identify measurable outputs from Champions, what existing metrics are there that we can use (e.g. University sustainability ranking?).

The need for evaluation milestones throughout the project was also discussed with the following suggestions made:

- Present progress against evaluation plan at community meetings to get feedback.

- Also survey the community confidence through Slido type evaluation in meetings.
- Use simple indicators (e.g. Red, amber, green) to measure how we are engaging with people/institutions. (i.e. Learn from Lisa Otty).

It was also noted that the evaluation plan needs to be scaled appropriately for the level of funding awarded.

NetDRIVE Meetings Plan

- There was general agreement in the proposed schedule of meetings for next year, however it was noted that the devil is in the detail. Early announcements are welcomed.
- Both outward facing (engage broad community) and inward facing elements (people who will be doing something about this) need to be incorporated.
- There was a suggestion to reformat the style of the meeting so that people can more flexibly engage, with:
 - Day 1 (outward) looking to engage the broad community, which might include people not already involved with the project who perhaps do not consider themselves as experts but want to learn more. This may involve:
 - Listening to talks and learning about sustainable DRI
 - Including an exhibition space for posters, demos
 - Day 2 (inward) looking at focused community discussions to enable the more engaged community members to have detailed discussions on specific areas.
- To address missing sections of the community there was the suggestion to look at announcements to see how we can make them targeted.
- Potential to engage with other activities:
 - SSI role for leading aspects in the future.
 - UK Compute Community Forum (Action 2 of the compute roadmap)
 - Culham AI growth server (potential for early engagement).

Appendix 4: Principles of Procurement

Introduction

Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) investments are an essential element of the UKRI research programme. Without continual investment in new technologies which enable research at the frontiers of intellectual exploration UKRI will not be able to deliver the breakthroughs in knowledge that the UK needs and expects.

The urgency of action to address the climate crisis has thrown a spotlight on the high and growing resource demands of digital research infrastructure. This includes both heavy electricity use, such that life-time costs of power may match or exceed purchase cost, and substantial environmental damage incurred during production (Figures 1 and 2).

It is not generally possible to rigorously account for the impacts of our digital supply chain, but awareness of the harms is imperative. While this gap in our knowledge is an undeniable aspect of our current situation, we should not tolerate continuation of this state of ignorance.

Figure 1: From Better Images of AI, illustrating the heavy dependence of AI on raw materials.

Lone Thomasky & Bits & Bäume / <https://betterimagesofai.org/>
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

We cannot at this point in time procure infrastructure without incurring harm. Nor can we demand changes from a supply chain which is driven by market forces far stronger than the UK academic sector. But we, like many other organisations and communities, have a strong commitment to achieve net zero by 2040 and need to be making firm steps in that direction.

The economic benefits of research investment in general have been estimated as £9.90 for every £1 invested¹. There is less clarity about the environmental benefits of research investment. The case for large procurements needs to carry explicit justification of the need for new infrastructure rather than upgrading existing facilities (even if a funding

call specifies a new infrastructure, it needs to be clear that the host institution can justify the approach being taken against national and organisational sustainability targets).

These principles set out different areas of concern and steps that can be taken to add transparency and evaluate options for mitigating impact.

Ensuring Environmental Harms are Proportionate to Benefits

Spending on research, as noted above, delivers a high return on investment. For financial costs, this has been verified by independent assessment. In the case of environmental costs, we do not have a clear evaluation of the benefits.

Specific forecasts of benefits should be provided and assessed, and an effective governance process put in place to ensure that benefits are delivered, with corrective action to be taken if benefits fall short.

Consideration should be given to the siting of facilities. Many data centre operators are locating their infrastructure in Scandinavia to take advantage of the combination of low costs and low carbon footprints.

Full Life-cycle Analysis

All stages of the hardware lifecycle should be included in the assessment of environmental impact, including the full supply chain, use phase, and end of life. For example, hardware designs which enables a high rate of recovery of rare Earth elements used in manufacture are preferable provided they can comply with performance and price constraints.

Use Phase

Analysis of use phase impacts should include total power use and at least four aspects of the impacts of this power demand on the carbon footprint of the national grid supplying the power: the national average carbon intensity of power, a market-based value, a regional value, and a marginal generation value reflecting the impact of adding to the existing grid load (more details in Appendix 1). These different metrics highlight the different ways in which a large facility can impact on our national trajectory to net zero. All metrics should include explanatory notes giving provenance information, key assumptions, and, where possible, standards used.

Environmental Cost of Information Technology Supply Chain

Business cases should demonstrate awareness of environmental impact of supply chains, including the scale of greenhouse gas emissions and environmental degradation associated with extraction of raw materials. Reasonable steps should be taken to mitigate and avoid environmental harms (for instance, favouring supply chains which have certifiable mitigation measures in place²). **Credible bounds on the scale and scope of unavoidable environmental harms must be provided.**

If direct estimates of hardware embodied carbon are not available, estimates should be used. This can be based on published coefficients related to the area of printed integrated circuits³. The footprint of raw materials should also be accounted for. An analysis of the sector suggests raw materials account for around 40% of embodied carbon⁴, in the absence of robust information about a specific supply chain

When accounting for the carbon footprint of the power used in production of printed circuits, the four distinct aspects of power usage described above should be assessed.

End of Use

Demonstrate awareness and understanding of the risks of substantial further environmental harms associated with inappropriate disposal of hardware after decommissioning and evidence ability to manage this risk through use of reliable and certified contractors, avoiding international movement of waste where possible.

Progression and Compensatory Actions

Progress towards net zero will require significant adjustments. Procurements should not only consider the current supply chain but also look at the ability of the supply chain to demonstrate a capability and commitment to reduce emissions in line with net zero targets.

Compensatory actions which mitigate or undo the harm caused by emissions may also be taken into account but should not conceal transparent reporting of emissions.

Appendix 5: The carbon footprint of power generation

There are many ways in which the act of drawing power from the national grid impacts on the carbon footprint of the park of generation facilities which feed into the grid. As in many complex systems, there is no universal metric, but there are a range of widely used metrics which reflect different aspects of the impact⁵.

The national average carbon intensity of power

An annual figure for carbon intensity of power is published by DSIT⁶ for use in reporting to DSIT. This approach allocates the total footprint of power generation in the UK across all consumers in proportion to the quantity of power that they draw. It gives a fully transparent, robust, and powerful view of the national usage of power.

Market based carbon intensity

Many organisations also report a market-based carbon intensity, based on following the money. Organisations in the UK can choose to pay for electricity generated from renewable sources. This does not completely remove their dependency on the fossil fuel power stations without which the national grid could not deliver reliable power, but paying for power from renewable generation can support progression towards net zero.

The regional carbon intensity

Regional carbon intensity, as published by the National Grid, shows the variation of carbon dependency in different parts of the country. There are huge challenges in transforming the national power infrastructure which result in a slower pace of transition in many parts of the country, while other regions may already be carbon free for extended periods. The regional carbon intensity provides an important metric of carbon load associated with choice of location.

Marginal carbon intensity

The marginal carbon intensity reflects the carbon cost of additional generation used to match any additional load. In the UK this will often be gas generation, especially during times of peak consumer demand for power. This metric is particularly valuable in showing the benefits of reducing power demand during periods of high load on the grid.

Jubilee Mine, South Africa - 6,500 tonnes of copper

<https://www.dillonmarsh.com/copper>

[Appendix 5: Reflections from Champions](#)

Kirsty Pringle

This meeting was the first NetDRIVE gathering since the Champion roles were announced, and it was great to attend as a newly appointed Champion - though it certainly made everything feel much more real! The meeting provided a really valuable opportunity to meet the other Champions in-person and to hear about each other's plans. What really struck me was how diverse our plans are. There's plenty of scope for collaboration, but also a real variety of ideas and approaches, which is exciting.

I found Dr Lisa Otty's talk particularly inspiring. She spoke about being part of the team behind the [Digital Humanities Climate Coalition Toolkit](#), and it was great to hear how it came together through a shared recognition of need. Our [Green RSE SIG](#) group is currently at the stage of shaping lots of ideas into concrete actions, so it was motivating to learn from a group that's already further along that path. We're working on developing a grassroots green RSE policy, co-written with RSE leaders, and Lisa's example of a collaborative, community-driven approach really resonated with me.

On a more personal note, although I've been to Durham for work a few times before, I had never actually walked along the river. It's beautiful, it's a bit like wandering through a remote jungle, until you suddenly emerge right in the middle of town!

Michael Rudgyard

Meeting the team and understanding the Netdrive project and vision

Overall the meeting was a great opportunity to meet members of the Netdrive team, and particularly the other Netdrive Champions – through both formal meetings and discussions, and through informal social events on the Wednesday and Thursday evenings. With regard to the former, the individual presentations were very useful to understand the skills and interests each of the champions bring. Similarly, the presentations of the Community Projects allowed us to see what projects had been funded to date and what their objectives were.

From my perspective, and as someone who had attended previous Netdrive meetings as a speaker but not one of the team, it might have been useful to spend some time at the beginning of the meeting in order to explain the project in more detail: eg. the overall vision, the funds available, project reporting requirements, the deliverables expected, and how the champions might help to bring particular focus to the project as a whole.

Invited Speakers

The talks were very interesting, well-delivered. and covered a reasonable number of subjects that might be of interest to the community. I would say, however, that grouping the talks together and possibly having more of these might help us attract more attendees (either in situ or remotely) – given peoples' busy lives, a more concentrated agenda might be more attractive and garner more interest than a few talks over three days.

Break-out sessions

In my experience, break-out sessions and working groups can be a bit hit-and-miss, depending on the subject, the size of the group, and the ability of the group to focus on the questions being asked (or indeed how well the question has been posed). Mediated sessions (across larger groups) can often be more productive, as pointed out by a couple of the other champions. In the absence of any budget for professional mediators, perhaps we can use the champions and/or the speakers to mediate, possibly following a round-table discussion that might get the sessions started. The scope and context of the sessions can also be planned ahead of the discussion and be clearly articulated in the agenda.

The Green Skills breakout was perhaps the best organized session, but sadly the scope of the questionnaire was too detailed for the time allocated in this case.

It may be the case that a day of any future meetings could focus on a particular area of sustainable research infrastructure. This might lead to a larger audience on that particular day with a common interest, and possibly more constructive group discussions.

Lorna Smith

The three-day Net Drive AGM brought together the newly funded projects and champions and focused on developing and defining a series of working groups. I found this a very positive meeting and came away with a number of ideas, thoughts and areas for further reflection.

A theme throughout the meeting was around how Net Drive makes a tangible difference to the sustainability of DRI, now and in the future. Is there a risk Net Drive generates lots of valuable insight and discussion, but fails to deliver tangible benefits? I came away with a view that there is no silver bullet and success will be shown in a number of ways. For example, through explicit measurement of emission reduction, but also from tracking the success of training activities, monitoring of the production and implementation of action plans and tracking the impact of best practice activities.

The meeting led me to reflect on Net Drive's potential to act as a trusted authority on sustainability for the DRI community and what this would look like. Yes, Net Drive can and will act to guide and support users and service providers to incorporate sustainability into their daily practice. But as a trusted authority, we can potentially make a larger impact, looking to ensure sustainability considerations are integrated into procurement processes and into funding calls. The concept of Net Drive as a trusted authority was raised a number of times throughout the meeting and is an area I plan to reflect on more.

The meeting confirmed the importance of monitoring and providing evidence/data to make a step change in the way DRI is used. For example, providing users with knowledge around the emissions associated with their use of DRI and offering alternatives and choice in the way they work, came through as key points throughout the meeting. Dashboards with usage data and emissions calculations, training and dissemination of information around how DRI is procured and commissioned, education around comparative sources, all were raised as important.

Finally, as a new champion, I was struck by the opportunity we, as a cohort of champions, have to make a difference. Sharing thoughts and ideas with the champions, hearing about their plans for their roles, led me to consider how best to collaborate with them and how best to utilise our collective power to maximise our impact.